

Ion-Solvent Interaction in Mixed Solvents : Viscosity of Bromates, Iodates and Sulphates of Potassium and Sodium in Dioxane-Water Mixtures at Different Temperatures

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The viscosities of the bromates, iodates and sulphates of potassium and sodium at 10, 20 and 30% dioxane-water mixtures (by wt.) have been measured at 30, 35, 40 and 45°. The data have been analysed in terms of Jones-Dole equation :

$$\eta_r = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC$$

The values of the constants A and B indicate ion-ion and ion-solvent interaction respectively, and ion-ion interaction is of the order $SO_4^{2-} > IO_3^- > BrO_3^-$ and ion-solvent interaction order is $BrO_3^- > IO_3^- > SO_4^{2-}$.

THE viscosity measurements of $KBrO_3$, $NaBrO_3$, KIO_3 , $NaIO_3$, K_2SO_4 and Na_2SO_4 in dioxane-water mixtures (by wt.) have been carried out at 30, 35, 40 and $45 \pm 0.01^\circ$. The data have been interpreted in terms of the Jones-Dole equation¹ :

$$\eta_r = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad (1)$$

where η_r is the relative viscosity of the solution, C is the concentration of the electrolyte and A and B are constants. The coefficient A is due to the contribution from interionic electrostatic forces²⁻⁴, and B gives the measure of the order or disorder introduced by the ions into the solvent structure.

A review of the literature shows that no general theory has yet been developed for B-coefficient, however, it is a manifestation of ion-solvent interaction⁵. In the present investigation, interest, therefore, centres on the coefficient of B. The nature of the B coefficient as pointed out by Cox and Wolfenden⁶ is attributed to its specific additive character depending on the constituent ions. On the other hand Asmus⁷ used the entropy of hydration to correlate ionic B values and recently a single linear relationship between the ionic B values and molar entropy of hydration has been obtained by Nightingale⁸.

Experimental

The salts $KBrO_3$, $NaBrO_3$, KIO_3 , $NaBrO_3$, K_2SO_4 and Na_2SO_4 used were of E. Merck 'extra pure' variety. The SO_4^{2-} contents were estimated in the usual manner⁹. The preparation of solvents, and solutions were the same as described earlier¹⁰. The viscometric

technique were the same as that of Chackravarty and Prasad¹¹. The densities of the solutions and the solvents were determined by pycnometer (50 cc. capacity) with buoyancy correction and is same as that of Srinivasan & Prasad¹². All sorts of precautions were taken to check the evaporation of the solvent¹³. The time flow differs by 0.2-secs in 20 minutes and have an error of $\pm 0.04\%$. Density readings were precise upto ± 0.0002 gm/ml. i. e. an error upto 4 in 10^6 . The concentration range was from 0.1M to 0.001M.

Results & Discussion

Viscosities of the mixed solvents as well as those containing salts solutions under study were measured. The results have been analysed in terms of Jones-Dole equation¹ as the plot of $(\eta_r - 1)/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$ is linear. The intercept and the slope of the plot give respectively the coefficients of A and B. The coefficient A and B thus obtained for various salts are given in Table-1 and 2 respectively. The calculated values of $A^{1/4}$ are in good agreement with those of the observed one. The relative viscosities calculated from these values of A and B, are found to be in acceptable agreement with the experimental values.

A Values :

The different 'A' values (Table-1) of all the six salts studied indicate dependence of ionic interactions on the nature of the electrolyte and are all positive. The electrostatic ion-ion interaction and hence the value of 'A' is found to increase with the decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium when the concentration of the dioxane increases in the mixture. From

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TABLE 1

$A \times 10^8$ values in $l^{1/2} \text{ mol.}^{-1/2}$

Temp.°C	10%D	20%D KBrO ₃	30%D	10%D	20%D NaBrO ₃	30%
30	6.9	7.1	8.2	7.2	7.4	8.9
35	6.2	6.6	7.9	6.3	7.0	8.2
40	5.8	6.0	7.4	5.9	6.2	7.4
45	5.4	5.8	6.9	5.5	5.9	6.3
		KIO ₃			NaIO ₃	
30	7.2	8.1	9.6	7.8	8.7	10.2
35	6.7	7.3	8.9	7.5	8.4	9.7
40	6.0	6.8	8.0	7.8	7.9	9.1
45	5.4	6.0	7.2	6.6	7.2	8.4
		K ₂ SO ₄			Na ₂ SO ₄	
30	13.5	16.0	26.6	13.9	16.6	17.2
35	13.0	15.0	26.0	13.4	15.2	16.0
40	12.2	14.2	24.2	12.6	14.1	14.6
45	11.6	12.6	22.2	12.1	13.4	13.9

table-1, it is seen that the ion-ion interaction is of the order: $\text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{IO}_3^- > \text{BrO}_3^-$. Further, the value of 'A' decreases with the rise of temperature for all the salts which one should expect in view of more thermal agitation at higher temperatures and reduction of attractive forces.

Dependence of B on temperature :

According to Stokes and Mills¹⁵ the viscosity of a dilute electrolytic solution incorporate that of solvent plus the contribution from other sources. They are, η^E , the positive increase due to the shape and size of an ion ; η^A , the increase due to the alignment on orientation of the polar molecules by the ionic field and η^D , the decrease in the viscosity arising due to the distortion of the solvent structure by the ions. Therefore, B-coefficient can be discussed in terms of these viscosity effects at different temperatures.

The B-coefficient of all the six salts increases with the increase in temperature. This indicates that the viscosity decrease due to solvent structure, i. e. η^D is small and hence $\eta^E + \eta^A > \eta^D$ and 'B' is positive. The 'B' value is found to be of the order : $\text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{IO}_3^- > \text{BrO}_3^-$. Hence, it can be concluded that distortion of solvent structures or ion-solvent interaction is of the reverse order, i. e. $\text{BrO}_3^- > \text{IO}_3^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$.

Further according to Stokes & Mills¹⁵, the lesser the value of dB/dt , the greater is the ion-solvent interaction. In the present case the plot of 'B' vs 't' is linear and the slope dB/dt is found to be of the order, $\text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{IO}_3^- > \text{BrO}_3^-$. This indicates that the ion-solvent interaction is of the order $\text{BrO}_3^- > \text{IO}_3^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$, which confirms the above interpretation.

Dependence of 'B' on cation :

Ions with greater crystal radii and small surface change density, K^+ , would have a weak orienting effect in the first layer. Therefore, η^E and η^A will be small. Also there exists a considerable amount of distortion in the vicinity of such ions due to the competition between the ionic field and bulk structure and consequently η^D will be large. Thus 'B' will be smaller for K^+ salts than for Na^+ salts (Table-2). So the order of ion-solvent interaction is $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+$.

Dependence of 'B' dioxane content :

McRae¹⁶ has suggested that the dioxane molecule has two non adjacent dipolar groups whose moment cancel, so that the effective reaction field is probably greater than is indicated by microscopic properties. Hence, the frozen layers, as suggested by Frank and Evans¹⁷, around the cation be expected to be constituted of both the water molecules and the dioxane molecules possibly consisting more of the former than the

TABLE 2

B values in lit. mol⁻¹

Temp. °C	KBrO ₃			NaBrO ₃			
	10% D	20% D	30% D	10%	20% D	30% D	
30	0.0300	0.042	0.062	.065	0.089	0.104	
35	0.043	0.059	0.078	0.089	0.109	0.119	
40	0.058	0.076	0.098	0.104	0.122	0.134	
45	0.074	0.092	0.114	0.122	0.138	0.146	
		KIO ₃			NaIO ₃		
30	0.120	0.145	0.165	0.181	0.212	0.252	
35	0.152	0.164	0.175	0.210	0.235	0.264	
40	0.165	0.185	0.220	0.235	0.255	0.281	
45	0.185	0.205	0.245	0.263	0.278	0.295	
		K ₂ SO ₄			Na ₂ SO ₄		
30	0.248	0.275	0.348	0.262	0.291	0.385	
35	0.280	0.300	0.380	0.300	0.325	0.410	
40	0.305	0.330	0.415	0.330	0.352	0.438	
45	0.330	0.388	0.434	0.360	0.378	0.448	

latter kind of molecules ; whereas, the diffused layer would consist of loosely oriented water and dioxane molecules, the extent of orientation decreasing with the distance from the ion till the outermost layer has the same structure and composition as that of the solvent. When the dioxane content of the solvent increases, more dioxane molecules take part in constituting the diffused layer and thus promoting a sort of ordering effect in the solvation sphere and hence would lead to larger values of η^E and η^A and exhibit an increase in the value of 'B' with increase in dioxane content (Table-2).

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